

INFECTIOUS SPONDYLODISCITIS IN PATIENTS WITH CENTRAL VENOUS CATHETERS FOR HAEMODIALYSIS: A RETROSPECTIVE STUDY

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SUMMARY

Aim: To evaluate the prevalence of infectious spondylodiscitis associated with central venous catheters (CVC) for haemodialysis.

Methods: Descriptive and retrospective research. Clinical histories of 830 patients with a CVC for haemodialysis in our unit were reviewed from January 1999 to December 2010. Clinical data associated with spondylodiscitis were collected.

Results: Five out of 830 patients reported infectious spondylodiscitis associated with their CVC for haemodialysis. Of the five cases, the average age was 66 years (range 59–72 years), there were four females and one male. Three had diabetic nephropathy. Site of CVC: four jugular, one femoral. Signs and symptoms: fever and leucocytosis 100%, lumbar pain 85%; positive blood cultures 60%; computed axial tomography and magnetic resonance imaging showing signs suggestive of spondylodiscitis or epidural abscess 100%.

Conclusions: Although rare, infectious spondylodiscitis is a serious complication in haemodialysis patients with a CVC as vascular access. It is essential that any alarming sign of infection to be recorded daily and appropriate treatment to initiate in order to avoid fatal complications.

KEY WORDS Catheter-Related Infections; Haemodialysis; Nursing Care; Spondylodiscitis.

INTRODUCTION

The proportion of prevalent patients on haemodialysis using a central venous catheter (CVC) as vascular access has increased considerably in recent years in many European countries, Canada and the United States. In Italy, Germany, France and Spain, the number of catheters has doubled or tripled (Ethier et al. 2008). This increase is related to certain features of current patients requiring haemodialysis: ageing, swift progression of kidney disease, high cardiovascular comorbidity and lower serum albumin levels. CVCs are considered the last resort in Vascular Access due to poor patient outcomes and their association with a high risk of infection and infection-related death, increased episodes of hospitalisation and higher health-care-related costs (McCann et al. 2010). Patients on haemodialysis (HD) who have a CVC have greater mortality risk than patients with an arteriovenous fistula (relative risk 1.79 vs. 1.29, respectively) (Pisoni et al. 2009).

Patients with chronic kidney disease (CKD) are susceptible to a diverse range of infections, as a consequence of chronic immunosuppression and invasive medical procedures. Although patient susceptibility to infection is dependent on factors such as primary renal disease, comorbidity, nutritional status and age, it is evident that prevention

and control of infection constitutes a fundamental component of the nursing care of this patient population (Pugh-Clarke et al. 2011).

Infectious spondylodiscitis (IS) is a rare infection (2–4% of all cases of osteomyelitis) affecting the vertebrae and intervertebral spaces (Pintado-Garcia 2008). *Staphylococcus aureus* is the predominant causal infectious agent, it is responsible for 3% to 74% of CVC bacteremia in patients requiring HD (Troidle et al. 2007). Although an uncommon complication, IS is a serious condition among HD patients, so early detection is imperative (Tsuchiya et al. 2004).

The purpose of this paper is to evaluate prevalence and clinical development of IS associated with patients who have a CVC for haemodialysis in our unit.

PATIENTS AND METHODS

This was a retrospective descriptive study. The clinical histories of patients with a CVC for HD in our unit were reviewed from January 1999 to December 2010. Five patients presented with IS related to their haemodialysis catheter. Demographic and clinical data were collected: age, gender, cause of kidney disease, catheter characteristics (insertion site, type, duration), possible causes of microbial agents, clinical signs and symptoms of patient, diagnostic tests performed, treatment and clinical course.

RESULTS

During the period of the study, the number of prevalent patients with CVC on our HD programme was on 830 patients, of whom, five patients presented with IS as a complication. This is an incidence of one episode per 250 patient-years. The clinical characteristics of the patients with IS are shown in Table 1.

The mean age of patients was 66 years (range 59–72 years). There were four women and one man. The most common kidney disease was diabetic nephropathy. All patients had a tunnelled CVC. Most catheters were inserted into a jugular vein (four patients) and only one was inserted into a femoral vein. The mean time of CVC implantation was 32 months (range 8–103 months). All catheters were of Tesio® type. The most common signs and symptoms were: fever/leucocytosis 100% and back pain 85%. The clinical manifestation of an epidural abscess can be initially nonspecific, but once it manifests itself, it follows a similar progression: back pain, radicular (nerve) pain, sensorimotor impairment, bladder dysfunction and finally paralysis. Once established it is irreversible.

Three patients showed positive blood culture (one *Staphylococcus aureus*, one *Staphylococcus epidermidis*, one *Staphylococcus lugdunensis*). Only one patient had a negative blood culture and the other had an unknown blood culture. The imaging tests (computed axial tomography and magnetic resonance imaging) in all cases were consistent with an epidural abscess.

The initial antibiotic treatment was vancomycin, which was modified following the blood culture results.

Because the symptoms were non specific diagnosis was delayed and all patients succumbed to their illness. All patients died.

Table 1: Clinical characteristics and clinical evolution of studied patients with infectious spondylodiscitis (MRI: magnetic resonance imaging; CAT: computed axial tomography).

Patient history	Vascular access	Cultures	Clinical presentation	Imaging tests	Treatment	Clinical evolution
Man 64 years old. Diabetic nephropathy	Jugular catheter Tesio® type	<i>Staphylococcus aureus</i> positive blood culture	Lumbar pain, fever and leucocytosis	MRI: spondylodiscitis T6-T7	Cloxacillin + Ciprofloxacin	Paraparesis died from cardiopulmonary arrest
Woman 72 years old. Unknown nephropathy	Jugular catheter Tesio® type	–	Lumbar pain, fever and leucocytosis	MRI: spondylodiscitis L4-L5 and anterior epidural abscess Ga-69 scan increased uptake	Cefotaxime + ceftriaxone	Deteriorating focal neurological signs died from stroke
Woman 69 years old. Diabetic nephropathy	Femoral catheter Tesio® type	<i>Staphylococcus lugdunensis</i> positive blood culture. Negative catheter culture. CAT-guided puncture D12: <i>S. lugdunensis</i>	Lumbar pain, fever and leucocytosis	X-ray: D7–138 y D12-L1 erosion, with increased paravertebral space CAT: spondylodiscitis D7-D8 and D12-L1 Ga-69 scan increased uptake	Cloxacillin + amikacin	Temporary clinical improvement died from myocardial infarction
Woman 72 years old. Amyloid nephropathy	Jugular catheter Tesio® type	<i>Staphylococcus epidermidis</i> positive blood culture. Negative catheter culture. Negative CAT-guided puncture culture	Lumbar pain, fever and leucocytosis	CAT and MRI: spondylodiscitis L5- S1 Ga-69 scan increased uptake	Vancomycin	Died from stroke
Woman 59 years old. Diabetic nephropathy	Jugular catheter Tesio® type	Negative blood culture. Negative catheter culture	Lumbar pain, paraparesis, fever and leucocytosis	CAT and MRI: spondylodiscitis L3- L4	Vancomycin + ceftazidime	Progressive neurological deterioration died from myocardial infarction

DISCUSSION

The incidence of IS in HD patients is low, with a variable incidence in different studies. Abid et al. (2008) described 13 cases of IS in a period of 10 years, with an approximate incidence of one episode every 215 patient-years (Abid et al. 2008). Philipneri et al. (2003) reported eight cases in a population of

162 patients over a period of four years (incidence of one episode every 80 patient-years) (Philipneri et al. 2003). Tsuchiya et al. (2004) described nine cases over a period of four years, while Helewa et al. (2008) found 22 cases in a population of 2,647 patients in a six year period. Kessler et al. (1993) reported only two cases of 1,445 patients studied in one year at 27 centers. In our audit, the incidence of IS complication (one episode per 250 patient-years) is not significantly high.

With regard to patient characteristics, our study suggests that female gender, diabetes, and older age are risk factors for developing IS, although numbers in our study are small. Our findings are supported by other studies (Philipneri et al. 2003; Tsuchiya et al. 2004; Abid et al. 2008). The literature refers to other predictors such as duration of haemodialysis, high levels of beta2-microglobulin, parathyroid hormone and alkaline phosphatase (Leone et al. 2001) or urinary tract infection (Troidle et al. 2004).

Fever, back pain and leucocytosis presented as symptoms suggestive of IS, although their lack of specificity delayed early diagnosis. Back pain or neck pain and fever occurred in other studies such as identification signs of IS (Tanaka et al. 1999; Philipneri et al. 2003; Tsuchiya et al. 2004; Abid et al. 2008). However, leucocytosis is not invariably present in previous studies (Tsuchiya et al. 2004; Abid et al. 2008). Individuals with an arteriovenous fistula have a significantly reduced risk to develop IS. From the six cases reported by Troidle et al. (2004) only one had a fistula, and the 13 cases reported by Abid et al. (2008), the incidence of IS was four times greater in patients with a CVC than in patients with a native fistula.

In our sample, only one patient had a negative blood culture. The negative blood culture ratio in other published studies varied from 23% to 50% (Philipneri et al. 2003; Tsuchiya et al. 2004; Abid et al. 2008). Concerning the responsible micro-organism, our sample had a variety of responsible organisms, yet in other studies, infection by Gram-positive organisms was the most common (Philipneri et al. 2003; Tsuchiya et al. 2004; Abid et al. 2008). It is important to note that Cottle and Riordan (2008) reviewed the available literature on IS and provided recommendations on management, particularly regarding the identification of the causative agent and antimicrobial therapy. The review found that no randomised controlled studies of antimicrobial therapy were identified in the literature search and there appear to be no European-wide consensus guidelines on investigation and management.

Cottle and Riordan (2008) suggest that unless the patient is severely unwell antimicrobial therapy should be delayed until a microbiological diagnosis is established. If initial blood cultures are negative then a CT-guided biopsy should be conducted.

In our audit, as in others, magnetic resonance imaging was the mainstay of diagnosis. Its advantages include the capability for simultaneous multiplanar visualization of bone, disk and neural structures. The most sensitive criteria for diagnosis of spinal infection include evidence of paraspinal or epidural inflammation, contrast enhancement of the disk, hyperintensity or fluid-equivalent Signal Intensity on T2-weighted images, and erosion or destruction of the vertebral endplates on T1-weighted images (Ledermann et al. 2003).

All of our patients died, probably due to late diagnosis (between two and four weeks) and the rapid evolution of the infectious process (between two and five weeks after IS diagnosis). The mortality rate related with IS in the published studies varied from 8% to 46% and was associated with cardiovascular comorbidity (Abid et al. 2008) as in our study. (See Table 1)

IMPLICATIONS FOR PRACTICE

The onset of fever with back pain in a patient with a CVC must alert us to the suspicion of IS. It is essential that any sign of infection must be recorded daily and appropriate treatment must be initiated in order to avoid fatal complications.

Nursing protocols to ensure the management of connections and disconnections of all catheters types (tunnelled and untunnelled) are crucial (Crespo et al. 2011). Nurses must assess signs of inflammation or infection before each HD session and ask the patient specific questions about pain/fever/feeling unwell. The presence of exudate or any other sign always indicates an unhealthy catheter, so nurses must be careful in assessing any exudate or discharge from the catheter. Even if blood or exudate cultures are negative, fever and leucocytosis must be monitored. Systematic monitoring of all aspects of CVC insertion and care is vital for early identification and ongoing audit (Moya et al. 2006).

CONCLUSIONS

Although rare, IS is a serious complication in patients requiring haemodialysis who have a CVC as vascular access. Risk factors for developing IS have been identified in our small study as older age, diabetes and female gender. When a patient with a CVC presents with back pain along with fever and/or leucocytosis we must suspect IS, and confirm it by imaging techniques.

CONFLICT OF INTEREST

No conflict of interest has been declared by the authors.

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